

[white paper]

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The inner structure of time

Open Mathematics Collaboration*[†]

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Abstract

Based on the idea that time is computation, we discuss one interpretation regarding the inner structure of time that explains quantum superposition.

keywords: time, quantum superposition, graph

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/chmqy/download>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6672667>

Introduction

1. This white paper is the *evolution* of [1, 2], inspired by [3].
2. According to the *Wolfram Model* [3–6],

time = computation.

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Notation

3. $R_i :=$ binary relation
4. $(a, b) :=$ ordered pair
5. $r :=$ rule that transforms R_i into R_j
6. $\subset :=$ proper subset relation

Spin up/down

7. Let $R_1 = \{(1, 0)\}$ and $R_2 = \{(0, 1)\}$.
8. $r : R_1 \rightarrow R_2$
9. In the light of (2), in a physical system governed by r , **time is the edge of the graph** of Fig. 1, where each arrow represents one unit of time.
10. Classical time evolution $t_0 \rightarrow t_1 \rightarrow t_2 \rightarrow \dots$ then reads

$$(1, 0) \rightarrow (0, 1) \rightarrow (1, 0) \rightarrow \dots$$

Figure 1: Graph representing the spin flip.

11. Assign the following meaning to the vertices:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= |1\rangle := \text{spin up,} \\ 0 &:= |0\rangle := \text{spin down.} \end{aligned}$$

12. Thus, it is quite logical to assign (8) to describe the qubit

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle + |0\rangle).$$

13. A measurement of this quantum system occurring at time t_n results in the collapsed state $|1\rangle$ or $|0\rangle$.

14. Considering that the “length” of time is the same for each quantum computational calculation in (10), (13) yields a probability $1/2$ for the collapse of each state.

Time composition

15. Note that there are two arrows in the spin up/down system since

$$(1, 0) \equiv (1 \rightarrow 0).$$

16. Then the rule (8) is given by

$$r : (1 \xrightarrow{\tau} 0) \xrightarrow{t} (0 \xrightarrow{\tau} 1).$$

17. $t :=$ classical time

18. $\tau :=$ quantum time required to flip the spin of the quantum particle

19. Consider the following experiment

$$(1 \xrightarrow{\tau_0} 0) \xrightarrow{t_0} (0 \xrightarrow{\tau_1} 1) \xrightarrow{t_1} (0 \xrightarrow{\tau_2} 1) \xrightarrow{t_2} \dots,$$

where $|\tau_0| < t_0 < |\tau_1| < t_1 < |\tau_2| < t_2 < \dots$

20. If the observer measures the spin of the particle at t such that $t_0 < t < |\tau_1|$, then the spin collapses to $|0\rangle$.

21. If the observer measures the spin of the particle at t such that $|\tau_1| < t < t_1$, then the spin collapses to $|1\rangle$.

Final Remarks

22. In summary,

- (i) classical time := map between relations,
- (ii) quantum time := arrow within a graph.

23. *Is time a composite dimension?*

24. $\tau \in t$?

25. $\tau \subset \mathbb{C}$?

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [7, 8].

*Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Send your contribution to mplobo@uft.edu.br.

Open Science

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [9, 10].

How to cite this paper?

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+ **The Wolfram Physics Project**

<https://www.wolframphysics.org>

Agreement

The author agrees with [8].

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